

Trace determination of Pb, Cu, Cd and Zn in Ayurvedic drug, "Mahayograj Guggulu" via polarographic technique

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Abstract : Ayurveda is predominant among India's traditional health systems and Ayurvedic medicine constitutes around 84% of the sector. However, claims of several Ayurvedic products are often being criticized for not having any scientific evidence and general lack of standardization of raw materials. A D.C. polarographic method has been proposed for the determination of heavy metals like Pb, Cd, Zn, Cu etc. in Ayurvedic drug – "Mahayograj Guggulu" at mg/L level. The drug was digested with HCl + HNO₃. The analysis was performed using 0.1 M HCl (for Zn), 0.25 M acetate buffer (pH = 4.4 ± 0.1) for Cd, Cu, 0.1 M LiClO₄ (pH = 2.2 ± 0.1) for Pb. The concentration of metals were in the order Zn > Cd > Cu > Pb. The results were satisfactory and the developed method is simple, rapid and sensitive and can be applied to the microdetermination of the heavy metals in various Ayurvedic drugs.

Keywords : Mahayograj Guggulu, D.C polarography.

Introduction

Mahayograj-guggulu is a widely used Ayurvedic formulation. In a retrospective study for the frequency of usage, Mahayograj-guggulu ranked first in the hospital practice and second in the private practice.

It is a splendid combination of several bhasmas like Nag bhasm, Yashad bhasm, Mandoor, Raupya, Rassindoor etc. and herbs like guggulu and trifala.

Guggulu, the resinous material of commiphora mukul, the largest single ingredient of Mahayograj-guggulu has been mentioned to be useful in disorders of lipid metabolism in Ayurvedic literature 600 B.C.².

Hypolipidemic activity of guggulu has been shown by various workers³⁻⁵. However, guggulu as a single drug is rarely used in practice. Mahayograj-guggulu is the commonly used formulation.

This formulation is used for various Vat Rogas like – Arthritis, jaundice, cough and bile disorders, blood infections, fistula, obesity, Emaciation, myalgia, hyperlipidemia and also in gynae problems.

Fig. 1. Direct current polarogram of lead in Mahayograj-Guggulu.

Fig. 2. Direct current polarogram of copper in Mahayograj-Guggulu.

Research material : One gram of drug was taken and it was digested with HCl + HNO₃ using dry ash method⁶.

Note

Table 1. Trace analysis of Pb, Cd, Cu, Zn in Ayurvedic drug – "Mahayograj Guggulu"

Trace metal	Supporting electrolyte	Halfwave potential as $E_{1/2}$ in volts vs (SCE)	Conc. (ppm)			% Error	Mean deviation	Standard deviation
			Taken	Found	Mean			
Pb	LiClO ₄	-0.39	1	1.37 1.29 1.31	1.32	0.32	0.003	0.04
Cu	Acetate	-0.10	2	2.16 2.03 2.03	2.07	0.03	0.003	0.07
Cd	Acetate	-0.60	4	4.83 4.50 4.72	4.68	0.17	0.003	0.16
Zn	HCl	-1.1	15	14.98 15.12 14.98	15.02	0.001	0.006	0.08

Fig. 3. Direct current polarogram of cadmium in Mahayograj-Guggulu.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade purity. Their solutions were prepared in triple distilled water. The C-V data for test solutions were recorded after passing pure nitrogen gas in the test solutions. 0.001% Triton X-100 was used as maxima suppressor. A digital D.C. polarograph CL-357 (Elico) was used to record current voltage data. This equipment has three electrode assembly, dropping mercury electrode as working electrode, calomel as reference electrode and platinum as counter electrode. Dropping mercury electrode had characteristics $m = 2.422$ mg/s, $t = 3.5$ s and $h = 60$ cm. Elico digital pH-meter was employed to measure the pH of solutions. A stock matrix standard solutions of zinc, lead, copper and cadmium (0.025 M) were prepared by dissolving calculated amounts of Pb(NO₃)₂, Cd(CH₃COO)₂ and ZnSO₄, Cu(NO₃)₂·3H₂O in triple distilled water.

Fig. 4. Direct current polarogram of zinc in Mahayograj-Guggulu.

Electroanalytical determination : The nature of the supporting electrolyte plays a significant role in polarographic analysis. After detailed study carried out in different buffers it was found that 0.25 M acetate buffer (pH = 4.4 ± 0.1) is an ideal medium for trace analysis of Cd and Cu, 0.1 M HCl for zinc and 0.1 M LiClO₄ (pH = 2.2 ± 0.1) for Pb. To the sample solution taken in pyrex-polarographic cell including 2 ml of buffer solution, we add 0.1 ml of 0.001% Triton X-100 and remaining required volume of distilled water. After that the polarographic cell was purged with N₂ gas for 15 min. To ascertain the presence of the said metal ions in the sample, a known quantity of stock matrix standard solution of each metal ion was added to the analyte and polarograms were recorded (Figs. 1-4).

Ayurvedic system of medicine uses oxides/herbal complexes of a number of metals like – gold, silver, copper, iron, zinc etc. An analysis of sample of Ayurvedic herbal medicine product found that 20% of them contained metals like Pb, Hg, Cd and As at levels that could be toxic. Metals like Na, Mg, Al, Ca, Sn, Pb, Mn, Cu, Zn, Fe, Ni, Ga, Zr etc. and non-metals – Si, P, As, Se etc. have been determined in the medicinal plant *crinum latifolium* by AAS⁷. Pb has also been determined in *smilax myosotiflora* by AAS⁸. Cu, Zn, Pb and Cd are determined in various chinese medicines⁹⁻¹⁹. Arsenic^{20,21} and mercury are also determined in various chinese medicines. Twenty bhasmas have been analysed by instrumental neutron activation analysis for the presence of toxic elements in them²².

Results and discussion

The results obtained from the study of Mahayograj-guggulu in parts per million range are presented in Table 1 which shows that the percentage error is small as 0.32, 0.03, 0.17 and 0.001 respectively for Pb, Cu, Cd and Zn in LiClO₄, acetate buffer and HCl. Mean deviation is found to be 0.003, 0.003, 0.003, 0.006 and standard deviation is found to be 0.04, 0.07, 0.16, 0.08 respectively for Pb, Cu, Cd and Zn.

For Mahayograj-guggulu, a large dose of 12 g/day has been prescribed in ancient ayurvedic texts²³, smaller doses from 3 to 5 g a day are usual in the present day practice.

But if in bhasmas, heavy metal concentration exceeds, it may pose harmful effects on our body as –

- (i) Higher concentrations of copper is responsible for Menke's disease and Wilson's disease.
- (ii) High levels of zinc causes nausea, gastric ulcer, pancreatitis, anemia and excessive salivation.
- (iii) The major biochemical effect of Pb is its interference with heme synthesis which leads to hematological damage.
- (iv) High levels of cadmium causes kidney problems, anemia and bone marrow disorders.

Articles published in, "The Telegraph", Calcutta, India and "Times News Network" shows that Mahayograj-guggulu with silver and Makardhwaj, manufactured by Baidyanath, contains heavy amounts of Pb, Cd, Hg and As.

Tolerance limits for trace metals	
Element	Tolerance limit (ppm)
Pb	5.0
Cd	0.001
Cu	0.2
Zn	5.0

Conclusion :

The described DCP method for the determination of Pb, Cu, Cd and Zn in Ayurvedic drug is specific, sensitive and rapid with a simple approach comprising low cost instrumentation compared to the mass spectrometry and atomic absorption spectrophotometry.

The results obtained by DCP are quantitative and in good agreement in terms of precise measurement.

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